
**GLOBALIZATION AND ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT: NIGERIAN EXPERIENCE
FROM 1990-2018**

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of globalization on economic environment in Nigeria. Quantitative research methodology was adopted using expo-facto research design to analyze the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Secondary data were obtained from secondary sources using statistical bulletin of Nigeria covering the periods of twenty eight (28) years from 1990-2018. Secondary data were analyzed using multiple regression to generate study result. Based on the analysis of the study, findings revealed that globalization variable (foreign direct investment, FDI) is statistically significant to the economic environment (agricultural gross domestic product, AGDP) in Nigeria. Similarly, the result also showed that globalization variable (trade openness) is not statistically significant to the economic environment (agricultural gross domestic product, AGDP). The result can be interpreted that FDI has significant positive influence on the agricultural production while, trade openness has insignificant influence on agricultural gross domestic product. Study recommends Nigerian governments to adopt economic policies (such as tariff) to checkmate influx of goods into the country that will be detrimental to the environment. The reason is to protect the environment against use as a dumping ground or site for inflow of products that are obsolete. Finally, firms are advised to adopt eco-friendly technology in the manufacturing and energy sector to improve environmental performance and tackle climate change.

Keywords: Globalization, Environment, Foreign Direct Investment, Trade Openness, Agricultural Gross Domestic Production